

AIAL's comments on AI Act Art.50 Transparency Consultation

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ABOUT AIAL

The AI Accountability Lab (AIAL) is a dedicated research lab within Trinity College Dublin that is focused on ensuring that the wider AI ecology — from research and product development, to regulation — centres public interest, particularly, the most marginalised and disenfranchised in society. Our inquiries into AI accountability, therefore, span from studies of large systems, structures, and ecologies (such as the AI field itself and regulatory processes) to executions of audits and evaluations on specific AI models, tools, and training datasets. We recognize that AI accountability research is most impactful when it can inform the public, impacted groups, and policy makers. Thus, we aim for active policy translation of our (as well as field wide) research.

You can find more information about the AIAL on its website at <https://aial.ie/>.

AUTHOR BIO

Dr. Harshvardhan Pandit is a Research Fellow in the AI Accountability Lab in Trinity College Dublin. His research interests are focused on solving real-world challenges associated with privacy, legal and regulatory compliance. Dr. Pandit is a nominated technical expert by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB). Dr. Pandit is also a member of the National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI), and through it participates within CEN/CENELEC and ISO groups on cybersecurity, privacy, and artificial intelligence, and is the co-editor for the ongoing ISO/IEC 27560 PII Processing Records standard. Additionally, Dr. Pandit also engages with standardisation activities in IEEE, in particular regarding P7012 machine-readable privacy terms, and in W3C as the chair of the W3C Data Privacy Vocabularies and Controls Community Group (DPVCG) that develops interoperable vocabularies for privacy and data protection activities based on legal and practical requirements.

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Art.50 feedback

Question 1. Please provide practical examples of AI systems that directly interact with natural persons, as well as examples for which there is doubt and you would seek clarification or consider out of scope. For each AI system, determine whether the interaction with the AI system can be considered obvious from the point of view of a natural person who is reasonably well-informed, observant and circumspect. Consider in your answer how this interaction may be affected by the characteristics of natural persons belonging to vulnerable groups due to their age or disability.

AIAL's comments:

Article 3(1) of the AI Act defines an 'AI system' as "a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments;" This definition ensures a broad range of technology which uses "automated techniques", especially those based on classical machine learning approaches. are classified as AI technologies, and that their use constitutes an AI system. This is regardless of whether such systems are advertised as AI or not. This means any system or service which involves the use of automated machine-learning approaches, including use of LLMs, is classified as an AI system under the AI Act. Whether they are subject to specific obligations under the AI Act further depends on the nature and context of the AI system, for example to determine its risk level.

The concept of "direct interaction" referred to in the question is not defined within the AI Act itself. Therefore, we first establish the criteria under which an AI system is said to directly interact with natural persons.

1. The natural person is the user of an AI system i.e. they interact to operate the AI system, and therefore their involvement constitutes as a "direct interaction". For example, a person using an online LLM service directly interacts with the AI system as a user of the service.
2. The natural person is a subject of the AI system i.e. an 'AI subject' where the AI system operates on data about the person obtained from the subject themselves. For example, a camera using facial recognition systems to allow people to enter a premises based on confirming their identity against an existing database. Here, the person does not directly use the AI system in the same sense as the earlier example. Instead, the person is made aware of the interaction through means such as a notice. Since such a setup also consists of an AI system interacting with a person without an intermediary, it should also be considered a direct interaction.

3. From the above, we establish that "direct interaction" should not be determined from the perspective of the natural person, but rather whether the AI system directly interacts with a person through both active and passive actions.

Without this interpretation, natural persons who are passive in the context of such AI systems will not be aware of the existence of the AI system, nor that they are the subjects of it. Consequently, they will not be able to exercise their rights without this awareness.

For AI systems directly interacting with natural persons, it is not always necessary that such uses will constitute personal data and therefore be subject to the GDPR. For example, a machinery component utilising an AI component allows its operator to configure settings and control the process. Clearly, this is an example of a natural person having a direct interaction with an AI system. However, there is no personal data involved unless the AI system explicitly records the actions of the person in an identifiable manner. At the same time, there is also a vast scope for such cases to involve personal data, such as where users interact with an AI system or where people are subjected to AI systems. In such cases, it is highly likely that the AI system records some form of data about the person, and therefore performs personal data processing. Such AI systems are then subject to the GDPR and its relevant obligations. In particular, we draw attention to Article 13 regarding collection of personal data from the data subject for information to be provided when such direct interactions happen with the participation of the data subject.

The second part of the question asks whether such interactions can be considered "obvious" from the perspective of the natural person. The implications of this question are important as it could be satisfied by the person merely understanding that there is something called "AI" being involved in the system without understanding its implications, limitations, or consequences. The existence of a general right of the individual to be informed already exists in the EU legal framework. For example, within consumer protection as the necessity for knowledge without which a contract cannot be considered fair. And for example, in data protection under GDPR where the data subject cannot consent or object without sufficient information. Therefore, we suggest that the intent of the obligation be taken into account as establishing sufficient awareness regarding the AI system's operation and effects. As established above, the criteria for interaction can involve both active and passive natural persons as subjects. For active subjects, the AI system can provide such information as part of the interaction. However, for passive subjects, such information should be provided in a way that enables persons to understand its implications in a sufficient and comprehensible manner. Therefore, the obligation to ensure "natural persons concerned are informed" should be taken broadly to include sufficient and comprehensible information about the nature, type, purpose, and scope of the AI system rather than simply stating that they are interacting with an AI system.

This necessity arises especially for people who are vulnerable in context by virtue of physical or mental impairment. In addition, minors (children) and older adults should be considered vulnerable due to the perceived risks that they do not understand AI as a topic sufficiently to understand the implications when a system states it is using AI. Such declarations may, intentionally or unintentionally by design, be perceived as a mark of trust regarding the operations of the AI system rather than an acknowledgement of its limitations or risks. Therefore, the ability for such natural persons to be informed must also be taken to mean that their awareness is not simply regarding the existence of AI, but rather its limitations and risks to their being and in context of their vulnerabilities.

Question 3. If you are aware of any examples of notification techniques that can be employed with interactive AI systems, including embedded in their design, to duly inform natural persons that they are interacting with an AI system, please provide them in your response.

For each notification technique, determine whether the type and the content of the technique used for notifying a natural person is appropriate, including considering the characteristics of natural persons belonging to vulnerable groups due to their age or disability, the need for a clearly distinguishable and accessible manner and the timing of the notification.

Question 4. Are there aspects related to the scope or practical implementation of the transparency obligation for interactive AI systems under Article 50(1) for which you would seek further clarification?

The question asks for specific notification techniques to inform natural persons that they are interacting with an AI system. Recital 132 establishes the need for this by noting, "Certain AI systems intended to interact with natural persons or to generate content may pose specific risks of impersonation or deception irrespective of whether they qualify as high-risk or not." However, these are not the only risks which should be addressed, and we envision a broader need for the natural persons interacting with AI systems to be sufficiently informed to address these. As Recital 27 of the AI Act notes, "*Transparency means that AI systems are developed and used in a way that allows appropriate traceability and explainability, while making humans aware that they communicate or interact with an AI system, as well as duly informing deployers of the capabilities and limitations of that AI system and affected persons about their rights.*" Recital 65 further expands on this by stating, "*This process should ensure that the provider identifies risks or adverse impacts and implements mitigation measures for the known and reasonably foreseeable risks of AI systems to the health, safety and fundamental rights in light of their intended purpose and reasonably foreseeable misuse, including the possible risks arising from the interaction between the AI system and the environment within which it operates.*"

In the context of quality assessments, Article 15(4) states "High-risk AI systems shall be as resilient as possible regarding errors, faults or inconsistencies that may occur within the system or the environment in which the system operates, in particular due to their interaction with natural persons or other systems. Technical and organisational measures shall be taken in this regard." We interpret this as meaning that providing sufficient information to the natural persons interacting with an AI system may also be a necessary measure to reduce errors and to make the system's operation more resilient.

Therefore, we understand the intent of providing information as a notification to the natural person is meant as a measure to assist them in understanding the capabilities and limitations of that AI system, as well as establishing the availability of rights and controls. With this in context, we envision the following categories of notification techniques and analyse their implications towards this objective:

1. The AI system makes it clear to the natural person that the system involves the use of AI. It does not provide further information as to what "AI" constitutes of, which aspect of the system is actually AI and which is not, for what purposes AI is being used, and what are its limitations. We do not consider such persons to be sufficiently informed as the use of AI does not satisfy the intended transparency objective.
2. The AI system informs about the application of AI as above, but in addition provides information regarding the techniques or capabilities used, such as the use of recommender systems or LLMs. We also do not consider such persons to be sufficiently informed for the same reason as above.
3. The AI system informs about the application of AI as above, but additionally also provides information about the specific role of AI in the system and whether the use involves outputs or operations that have inherent risks to the natural person or their use of the system. We consider such persons to be sufficiently informed in terms of being aware of the nature and implications of interacting with an AI system.

Where there may be a large amount of information involved to satisfy the requirement to be considered informed, we envision designs that provide a summary or clearly indicate that the system's use of AI has important information that the natural person should take effort to understand. This can be done by, for example, creating an alert icon with AI and output risks with a link to further information on this topic. If this is not done, and the icon merely shows AI, it does not communicate any meaningful information to the natural person beyond the existence of AI. It is unreasonable to expect that the natural person possesses expertise to understand the technical limitations of AI technologies or that they are likely to have inherent errors such as biases, producing hallucinations, or simply being incorrect in an unpredictable manner. We therefore also consider that the average natural person cannot be assumed to have this capacity or expertise and therefore this is outside the scope of such persons being considered reasonably well-informed by default. And that the requirement for

being informed is precisely to establish such capacity in the natural person to be considered well-informed through information about the AI system as described here. In the context of vulnerable persons, in particular those who may not have the capacity to understand the implications of using AI, we ask that such risks in the use of AI be made more prominent in the notification.

Question 5. Please provide practical examples of AI systems that generate synthetic text, audio, image, or video content as well as examples of systems for which there is doubt and you would seek clarification or consider them out of scope.

If you are aware of any AI systems that may fall under one or more of the exceptions of Article 50(2), such as AI systems that perform an assistive function for standard editing or that do not substantially alter the input data or the semantics thereof, or systems that can be authorised by law for law enforcement purposes, please include them in your response.

The question relies on an understanding of "synthetic" content, which is contentious as it refers to a spectrum from all AI generated content being considered synthetic at one end to only those contents which cannot be matched in similarity to existing content being considered synthetic at the other end. For example, if an image is enhanced using AI techniques, whether the resulting image should be considered synthetic or not may be argued depending on its retained similarity to the original input image. Since this is a subjective criteria, we draw attention to the lack of a robust framework for the determination of whether an AI's output is considered synthetic regardless of its input.

For AI techniques which are generative in nature, such as LLMs, the output must be considered synthetic unless it is empirically and statistically proven that the output was present, with sufficient retained similarity, to earlier data. This is because of the inherent nature of generative AI techniques to manipulate data to such an extent that its outputs can no longer be said to be similar to any one particular input, and instead that they are entirely synthetic. This is also the reason such techniques are known to produce incorrect or out of context outputs, including hallucinations.

Question 6. Please provide examples of marking and detection solutions, including combinations of techniques, that can be employed to mark in a machine-readable format AI-generated or manipulated content and enable detection whether the content has been generated or manipulated by AI.

Question 7. For each of the solutions included in the previous question, please clarify whether there is relevant information that can help you competently assess their effectiveness, interoperability, robustness and reliability as far as this is technically feasible, taking into account the specificities and limitations of various types of content,

the costs of implementation and the generally acknowledged state of the art. Please also assess to what extent the detection mechanisms are accessible and enable people exposed to the AI generated or manipulated content to identify its origin.

The measures mentioned in the question can be broadly categorised as first regarding those applied at the time of generating content to indicate its provenance i.e., it was generated using AI, and second regarding those which apply on existing content in order to determine its provenance i.e., to determine whether it was generated by AI. We discuss them separately as these measures are applicable at different stages, and because they are implemented using different techniques. In our discussion, we rely on existing practices regarding measures to mark and detect provenance, and extrapolate similar uses to AI generated content.

Measures that 'mark' or 'declare' AI generated content can be seen to provide a visual or recognisable indication of provenance. Such measures are intended to provide transparency, or assert protections through branding, warnings, or notices, and are similar to those utilised currently, for example as visible watermarks within videos or documents. This will be relevant later in questions regarding deepfakes. Other measures which also mark AI generated content can be invisible, and such measures can be used to intentionally avoid recognition by users. For comparison, the AI framework in Chinese law has three categories of watermarks that are mandatory to be implemented by AI content generators. First is an 'explicit watermark' that must be visible to the user such as in prompt texts. Second as an 'implicit watermark' where images, videos, and audio contains invisible embedded information that must contain, at minimum, information on the service that generated them. And third as metadata declared at the file level which functions similar to existing metadata schemes for documents to declare their contents and provenance.

For measures that detect whether content has been generated by AI, they can only reliably work when their implementer is privy to an existing measure that has been embedded within the content to mark it as AI-generated. Such measures are likely to be provided by companies who also provide content-generation services, but it is also highly likely that they will not share technical details regarding these with others to protect IP or trade secrets. From the perspective of the AI Act, it is vital that any claim of such techniques is established within the boundaries of valid legal practices, in particular for claims made regarding the utility, performance, and availability of such 'AI-detection' services. Additionally, such techniques may end up being utilised in investigations in order to produce evidence. In this we specifically are referring to their use in use-cases such as universities assessing students, or organisations assessing job applications, where the outcome of the AI-detection process has a material impact on the natural person. We therefore consider these as forms of automated decision making under the GDPR where such techniques are used to determine whether content is AI generated and this involves an assessment of personal data. This

clarity is important as the AI Act does imply the existence of such techniques but does not explicitly state any particular obligation regarding their accuracy, performance, or interpretation under the GDPR.

Measures that claim to detect AI generated content have also been known to be immensely inaccurate. For example, in 2023 OpenAI reported that the accuracy of its 'AI classifier', developed after many iterations to detect whether an output was produced by ChatGPT, was so low (as in bad) that it decided to withdraw the tool. Till date, no further tools have been provided by OpenAI or any other platforms that reliably can be used to detect AI generated content.

In contrast, there has been a rapid and sharp increase in services that claim to detect AI generated content despite there being no technical evidence to support such capabilities at a fundamental level. Given that in the past, OpenAI has committed to developing digital watermarks for ChatGPT, Google has developed a watermarking service called SynthID, and Meta and Microsoft have indicated that they are looking into invisible watermarks, there is a reasonable likelihood that these tools are deployed before they have been thoroughly tested and have been proven to be effective beyond laboratory test cases. We therefore draw attention to the possibility of such services being used, whether intentionally or unintentionally, to meet the obligations of the AI Act. This is a dangerous development as they are likely to be used in situations explained earlier (universities, jobs, etc.), and where similar cases have also been considered as high-risk in Annex III for their perceived impact and harms.

Question 13. Please provide practical examples of generative AI systems that produce 'deep fake' AI-generated or manipulated image, audio, or video content that resembles existing persons, objects, places, entities, or events and would falsely appear to a person as authentic or truthful.

If you are aware of any AI systems for which the deep fake content may be considered to form part of an evidently artistic, creative, satirical, fictional or analogous work or programme, please include them in your response.

Question 14. Please provide practical examples of AI-generated or manipulated content for which you would seek clarification regarding its classification as a 'deep fake'.

Question 16. If you are aware of any examples of disclosure practices that can be employed with deep fake content to duly disclose the artificially generated or manipulated origin of such content to natural persons exposed thereto, please provide them in your response.

For each disclosure practice, determine whether the type and the content of the disclosure practice is appropriate for clearly, distinguishably and accessibly informing natural persons about the artificially generated or manipulated origin of the content and the timing of the notification.

In cases where the disclosure practice is used on deep fake content that forms part of an evidently creative, satirical, artistic, fictional or analogous work or programme, determine whether the disclosure is done in an appropriate manner that does not hamper the display or enjoyment of the work.

Question 20. Are there any other aspects related to the scope or the practical implementation of the transparency requirement for deployers of AI systems that generate deep fakes and text publications on matters of public interest under Article 50(4) for which you would seek clarification?

All generative AI services that allow users to create audio, image, or video content are effectively 'deep fake' generators as they are capable of generating content where existing persons, objects, etc. are placed in a manipulated and fictional context. However, such services do not restrict or inform their users about the responsible use of such deep fakes. The question enquires whether a deep fake may be considered artistic, creative, or satirical – because these categories allow representing people in fictionalised settings as part of speech, and whose expression is in general not restricted unless they cause or can cause harms. In reading through the terms, policies, and the instructions in interfaces of popular AI generation services, none provided such clarification or guidance to users, and in fact seemed to enable freely generating deep fakes. The only tangible restrictions were regarding the content itself, for example to prevent generating vulgar, sexual, or violent content.

Therefore, the regulation of these under the AI Act must require a proportionate measure from such AI content generation services to take responsibility for their services being used to produce deep fakes, and to ensure that such services are only used for the valid purposes where deep fakes can be safely used. Recent events have shown a marked increase in deep fakes being circulated online, especially without the consent of the individuals being imitated, and where they clearly do not satisfy any of the criterias where they can be considered as part of legitimate free expression of the creators' thoughts.

The proliferation of such deep fakes also has an impact on democracy, for example in the recent Moldovan Parliamentary Elections, deepfake videos were circulated targeting a particular candidate. Such non-consensual and harmful use of deep fake technology can also be a vector for foreign interference in democratic processes. It is therefore justified that providers of AI content generation services be required to have specific policies in place to address the creation of deep fakes, including providing guidance to users on responsible use,

ensuring that their outputs are not capable of systematically creating harmful content, and that they have an obligation to mark the deep fakes with not only the identity of the service or service provider, but also that of the user to ensure that malicious uses can be addressed effectively. This measure is aligned with the earlier measure on marking AI generated content.

For watermarking or otherwise marking deep fake contents to enable identification of these as AI generated, we support such measures. However, in our findings of current practices, we found examples where AI generative content providers have a branding on their generated output. We do not consider this as a sufficient measure to mark these videos as these are not intended to inform the consumers about the inherent nature and risks of such content, but instead serve to promote the content through branding and marketing. We also further consider such brand markings to be cumbersome for consumers, as they necessitate recognising, remembering, and knowing how to find them for any number of services.

Question 21. Are there aspects related to the AI Act's horizontal requirements in Article 50(5), including their interplay with the requirements in Article 50(1)–(4), for which you would seek clarification?

The AI Act assumes that AI systems utilising biometric categorisation and emotion detection are capable of doing so. However, such techniques have no scientific basis, and instead rely on flimsy statistical correlation and outdated pseudoscience to justify results. Their very presence carries risks to their subjects, and therefore requires that such subjects, at the very least, are informed of this risk to their privacy. Merely declaring their use cannot be considered as being informed.

Question 23. Are there any further aspects related to the transparency obligations under Article 50(1)-(5) for which you would seek clarification regarding their interplay with obligations in other Union or national legislation (e.g. data protection regulation such as Regulations (EU) 2016/679 and (EU) 2018/1725 and Directive (EU) 2016/680, Regulation (EU) 2024/900 on the transparency and targeting of political advertising or Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 on a Single Market For Digital Services)?

Under Art.22, the use of AI detection methods is automated decision making when used on personal data (e.g. job applications, exam results). This necessitates that such measures have human intervention, which is impossible with the mechanical nature of AI detection methods.